

The influence of brand image and brand awareness on purchasing decisions is moderated by brand ambassadors

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the effect of brand image and brand awareness on purchasing decisions moderated by brand ambassadors for Seiko 5 Sports watch products. A sample of 100 respondents and the data were processed using the Smart PLS 3 program. Brand image, brand awareness, and brand ambassadors all had a direct and significant positive effect on purchasing decisions, according to the findings. Brand ambassadors are unable to moderate the impact of brand image and brand awareness on purchasing decisions. This study adds to the body of knowledge/theory about the relationship between brand image, brand awareness, brand ambassadors, and purchasing decisions, as well as presents a novel brand ambassador approach as a moderator of the relationship between variables.

Keywords: Ambassador; Awareness; Brand; Image; Purchasing decisions

1. Introduction

Marketing's role in entering the globalization era, particularly in the fashion world, is critical as the company's spearhead in facing competition. Every business must be able to meet the needs of its customers and strive to create a product that outperforms its competitors. Product development efforts that are different and have advantages, especially in watch products, apart from being useful as a function to tell the time, but also for fashion. Now watches have also become a necessity for most people because people are increasingly busy and a very short time requires someone to have to know the time at all times so they can carry out their activities properly.

Many similar companies are popping up more and more and the products offered in a diverse market. With the rapid development of information technology today, it is easier for consumers to get products that suit their needs and desires. Consumers who need a product will find many choices of product attributes to consider. Thus, producers must be able to read consumer desires so that they can create a product that consumers can choose optimally.

At this time many watch manufacturers offer a variety of products to provide many choices that are suitable for use for the character of each consumer. Every producer is competing to gain success in the competition by improving the quality of the products they provide to consumers with the ultimate goal being a decision to buy from the consumer, which will have a major impact on the purchasing decision behavior of consumers.

Fierce competition shows that there are many product brands of the same type on the market. As a result, the competition between brands is very fierce. Therefore, creating a good brand image in the eyes of consumers is very important. According to [1], a brand image is a summary of consumer attitudes and perceptions about a specific brand. Consumer associations and memories serve as a reflection of brand image, which is consumer perception and belief. Brand can add value to products whether in the form of goods or services. A brand contains a company's promise to

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consumers to provide certain benefits, features, and services. The stronger the brand image in the customer's mind, the more confident the customer will be that they are or will be loyal to the product they purchase, and this influences their purchasing decision [2].

Another factor that influences coping opinions is brand mindfulness. Brand mindfulness is the capability of a implicit buyer to fete or remember that a particular brand is a part of order. Brand mindfulness can also be interpreted as the strength of a brand to be recalled by consumers and can be seen from the consumer's own capability to identify the brand in various conditions. Brand awareness and purchasing decisions are forms of consumer action because consumers know and recognize a brand. This becomes a reference for consumers in deciding to buy a product. So, it can be concluded that in deciding to purchase a product, consumers need information that will refer to the introduction of a product brand and make the product brand known and remembered by consumers [3].

In addition to brand image and brand awareness, there are other factors, namely brand ambassadors who have a very important role in influencing consumer purchasing decisions in buying products, so that it determines the success of marketing a product. [4] states that Brand ambassadors are artistic or identity icons, where they act as a marketing tool that represents the achievement of individualism and the commercialization of a product. Before deciding to buy a product, of course consumers have a certain reason for buying the product, for illustration consumers are influenced by brand ambassadors that companies use to vend their products or because these consumers formerly believe in the being brand image. Companies employ brand ambassadors to promote their products to impact or invite consumers. thus, brand ambassadors are generally chosen from various public figures who have popularity. According to [5] brand ambassadors are tools used by companies to communicate and connect with the public to increase product sales. This shows the role of brand ambassadors in increasing purchasing decisions by consumers to encourage product sales.

On many search sites on the internet related to the search for the best and fashionable men's watches in Indonesia, Seiko watch products are not at the top of the list. One of the superior products is the Seiko 5 watch, which is a legendary automatic men's watch. What's behind it? How is the relationship between brand image and brand awareness on purchasing decisions? In this study, the brand ambassador variable was added to see whether the brand ambassador could affect the strength of influence between the variables mentioned above.

So that from the description above, the formulation of the problem is arranged as follows:

- Does brand image affect purchasing decisions?
- Does brand awareness affect purchasing decisions?
- Does the brand ambassador affect the purchasing decision?
- Can brand ambassadors moderate the relationship between brand image and purchasing decisions?
- Can brand ambassadors moderate the relationship between brand awareness and purchasing decisions?

2. Literature Review

For companies, marketing activities have a very important role very important, because marketing activities are directed to create a turnaround that allows the company to maintain its viability. In addition, marketing activities are carried out to achieve company goals that are in line with expectations. Marketing management is one of the company's main activities to maintain business continuity, develop and make a profit. The marketing process begins long before the production of goods and does not end with sales. The marketing activities of the company must satisfy consumers even if they want to continue their business or if the consumer has a better overview of the company [6].

Marketing management includes the entire business system of planning, pricing, advertising and distributing goods or services that satisfy the needs of buyers. According to [7] explain that marketing management is a management activity based on its function which essentially seeks to identify what consumers really need, and how fulfillment can be realized.

The conclusion is that marketing management is an activity that is planned and organized which includes the distribution of goods, pricing and supervision of policies that have been made whose aim is to gain a place in the market so that the main objectives of marketing can be achieved.

Brand image as a consumer's impression or conviction, as shown by the associations that are established in their memory. A successful and recognized brand makes it possible consumers to recognize that the product can provide satisfaction for them, then compare it with existing alternatives and differentiate them from existing alternatives,

consequently increasing the likelihood of consumers buying. A company is said to be successful in branding a product or service, which can be seen from how the company instills in consumers a positive perception of the brand. Thus, consumers of a company are no longer confused in buying a product or service. Brand image is useful for positioning the company, products, markets and relationship with consumers. Most consumers always assume that when a company has a good brand image, the product is a quality product in their eyes, and vice versa, when a company has a bad brand image, the product is a product that has no value in the eyes of customers [8].

Brand awareness, according to Aaker, is customers' capacity to discern or recall that a brand is associated with a particular product category [9]. Consumers' accomplishments in brand recognition or recall serve as indicators of their brand awareness, which is the capacity to recognize companies under a variety of circumstances [10]. Brand awareness measures how many consumers in the market can recognize or remember the presence of a certain brand in a certain category, and the more aware consumers are of a brand, the easier it is to make a purchase decision. Anything that gets consumers to follow and pay attention to a brand can increase brand awareness [11]. The capacity of a potential customer to recognize or recall that a brand belongs to a specific product category is known as brand awareness [9]. Keller defines brand awareness as related to the strength of the brand in memory, which can be measured as the ability of consumers to identify brands with different conditions. Whereas Aaker argued that brand awareness is the ability of prospective buyers to remember the brand both between the product class and the brands involved, on the other hand Jacoby stated that brand awareness can influence purchasing decisions which will then increase loyalty [12]. Consumer awareness of a brand can be used by companies as a means to provide consumers with a deeper understanding of a brand. This awareness is expressed in the tendency of consumers to buy an already known brand, because people feel protected and eliminate numerous risks of use when they purchase a well-known brand. The capacity of potential customers to recognize or recall a brand within a specific category is known as brand awareness [13].

As cultural symbols of organizations or identities, brand ambassadors serve as marketing tools that symbolize the triumph of individualism, the grandeur of humanity, and the promotion of a product. According [14] a brand ambassador is a person who has earned the right to speak on behalf of a specific product. According to [15] a brand ambassador is a person who has the endorsement of several well-known public figures. Visibility (popularity), credibility (expertise), attraction, and power are qualities of brand ambassadors (strength). Companies utilize brand ambassadors to persuade or encourage people to use a product; the ambassadors are typically well-known celebrities. The appointment of brand ambassadors is usually motivated by the positive image they convey, so that they can represent the overall image of the product. The appointment of brand ambassadors is usually done for symbols that may represent wants, desires or needs that are easily acceptable to consumers. Usually represented by professional figure [16]. According to [17] Trendsetter brand ambassadors are often used as brand advocates in the marketing sector. A brand ambassador is someone who is enthusiastic about a product and can persuade or invite customers to buy or use it. According to [18] in general a brand ambassador is a brand representative who confirms a brand with its reputation; Brand ambassadors are typically brand representatives who mediate internal and external brand management and can significantly influence how customers perceive a brand or organization.

The variables listed above can influence purchasing decisions, and [1] defines consumer purchasing decisions as a process in which consumers are aware of a problem and seek information about a specific product or brand. According to [19] Financial economics, technology, politics, culture, products, costs, places, advertisements, empirical data, and people, and process all have an impact on purchasing decisions. So as to shape consumers' attitudes toward processing all information and arriving at a conclusion in the form of a response that appears as to which product to purchase. In the meantime [10] stated Consumer behavior is the study of how people, groups, and organizations choose, purchase, and use products, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs and aspirations. Consumer purchasing decisions are a subset of consumer behavior. Purchasing decisions are inextricably linked to a consumer's nature (consumer behavior), so each consumer has unique purchasing habits. It can be concluded that purchasing decisions are influenced by consumer attitudes when selecting a product to achieve the desired satisfaction. This is a consumer activity in which the consumer decides to purchase a fixed product; if the product changes, the consumer makes a repurchase decision.

Brand ambassadors, such as celebrities or other public figures, can assist consumers in making purchasing decisions. This demonstrates that using a celebrity in an advertisement as an endorser raises brand awareness [20]. A brand ambassador has a significant impact on brand awareness [18]. Brand Ambassadors have a significant and positive impact on the image of a company. The better the brand ambassador for a product, the better the brand image. A celebrity's accomplishments and personality are taken into account by the right brand ambassador. The compatibility between the brand and the celebrity's personality is the main objective of a brand ambassador. Positive consumer perceptions help to boost the reputation of a product brand. The appropriate brand ambassador can help to enhance the perception of the brand among consumers. The key for brand ambassadors is to ensure that the brand and the personality of the celebrity as an endorser are compatible. When celebrity characters are paired as brand ambassadors,

the brand's image improves [21]. As a result, celebrities must be chosen in accordance with the product because celebrities will represent the product image [22]. The presence of a brand ambassador has a significant impact on brand awareness [18]; [23]. Brand ambassadors significantly and favorably influence consumers' purchase choices [20]. In other words, the better the brand ambassador for the product, the better the purchase decision. Brand ambassadors are used to influence consumers. As a result, popular public figures are chosen as brand ambassadors. The average consumer's description of brand ambassadors demonstrates that consumers value brand ambassadors. Positive consumer perceptions of brand ambassadors will influence consumer purchasing decisions. Brand ambassadors are tools that businesses use to communicate with and connect with customers in order to increase product sales. This demonstrates the importance of brand ambassadors in improving purchasing decisions [24]. Brand ambassadors have a large influence on purchasing decisions [23]. Brand image is significantly and favorably impacted by brand awareness. Brand awareness is the recognition and retention of a brand by consumers. Contrarily, brand image refers to what customers believe and feel when they hear or see a brand. The brand image of a product will be enhanced by consumers' ability to recall that brand. Brand awareness is the capacity to identify and recall names of products and services. Contrarily, brand image refers to what customers believe and feel when they hear or see a brand. The associations and impressions connected to the brand will become more potent with time. Brand awareness affects purchase choices and has a big impact on brand image. [20]; [18]; [23]. Consumers at the top of their minds will choose the brand. Furthermore, products with a high brand awareness will have a larger market share. Consumer brand awareness will lead to more purchases.

3. Methodology

A research method is a scientific method for obtaining records that can be used for a specific purpose. A systematic way in which research activity is based on scientific properties: empirical, systematic and rational [25].

This research is quantitative. Quantitative research is empirical work that examines particular populations and samples, collects data using research instruments, analyzes quantitative/statistical data, and tests particular hypotheses [25].

A generalization domain known as "population" consists of items or people with unique traits that researchers have chosen to investigate and make conclusions from [25]. The population used by the researchers is Seiko 5 sports watch consumers living in Surabaya, Indonesia, with an unknown population (infinite population).

The sample represents a representation of the population's size and makeup. So, the sample is part of the population which is expected to represent the research population. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling. Because the population size is unknown, the sampling is carried out using the Lemeshow formula:

$$n = \frac{[\frac{Z_{\alpha}}{2} \cdot \sigma]^2}{e}$$

$$n = \frac{[1,96 \cdot 0,25]^2}{0,05}$$

Description:

n = number of samples

Z_{α/2} = value from the normal distribution table at the 95% confidence level = 1.96.

σ = standard deviation of 25%

e = error (error limit = 5%)

Based on the calculation above, the number of samples used 96.04 respondents were rounded up to 100 respondents.

The survey's replies are evaluated using the Likert scale. A Likert scale is used to gauge attitudes, views, and perceptions of social phenomena. To transform what is measured into an index quantity, the Likert scale is employed. For the creation of instrumental objects like assertions, these measurements act as a starting point. Responses were typically scored as follows for the quantitative analysis: I strongly agree received a perfect score of 5. I agree with a score of 4. Doubt was rated with a score of 3. On a 2-point scale, disagreement was rated. Score 1: I strongly disagree.

Regarding the metrics used as the basis for data collection:

- Brand image (X1): 3 indicators are 1) Strength; 2) Uniqueness; 3) Favourite.
- Brand awareness (X2): 4 indicators are 1) Brand recalls; 2) Brands recognition; 3) Purchases decision; 4) Consumption.
- Brand ambassador (Z): 3 indicators are 1) Attractiveness; 2) Trust; 3) Expertise.
- Purchase decision (Y): 4 indicators are 1) Stability; 2) Habits; 3) Recommendations; 4) Repurchases.

A research model framework, a description of all variables addressed in this study, can be constructed as follows:

Source: processed by Smart PLS3

Figure 1 Research Model Framework

3.1. Formulation of research hypothesis

Hypotheses are created based on the theories and ideas described above. In other words, from the theory and way of thinking, multiple hypotheses can be made as follows:

- H1: Brand image (X1) affects to purchasing decisions (Y).
- H2: Brand awareness (X2) affects to purchasing decisions (Y).
- H3: Brand ambassador (Z) affects to purchasing decisions (Y).
- H4: Brand ambassador (Z) can moderate brand image (X1) to purchasing decisions (Y).
- H5: Brand ambassador (Z) can moderate brand awareness (X2) to purchasing decisions (Y).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Evaluation of Measurement (Outer Model)

4.1.1. Test of validity

If the target variable's load factor value is more than 0.55, an indicator is deemed to be legitimate, Hair et al. in [26]. The output from SmartPLS3 will look something like this:

Reflex symbol effectiveness is evaluated using correlations between object values and variable values. When distinct letters of the same variable are extruded, it is said to be measured in reflected letters. Perception can be measured well by reflective markers. The aforementioned table demonstrates that the load factor values are higher than the advised value of 0.55. The X1.3 index has a minimum value of 0.582. The test's characters have convergence validity. The load factor for each statistic is depicted in the graph below;

Table 1 Outer loading result

No.	Indicators	ME 1	ME 2	X1	X2	Y	Z
1	X1 * Z	1.187					
2	X1.1			0.949			
3	X1.2			0.935			
4	X1.3			0.582			
5	X2 * Z		1.228				
6	X2.1				0.851		
7	X2.2				0.860		
8	X2.3				0.861		
9	X2.4				0.757		
10	Y1					0.813	
11	Y2					0.855	
12	Y3					0.843	
13	Y4					0.853	
14	Z1						0.851
15	Z2						0.883
16	Z3						0.906

Source: processed field data

Source: processed by Smart PLS3

Figure 2 Loading factor value

Cross loading values should also be used to check the effectiveness of reflex indicators.

The indicator is validated if the load factor of the target variable is higher than the load factors of the other variables. The loading factor for the X1 indicators (X1.1 to X1.3) is higher than for the other variables, as shown in the table above. The load factor of X1.1 for X1 is 0.949 greater than the load factor of X2 (0.366). Y (0.455) and Z (0.267). The same is true for other indicators. One block indicator predicts potential contracts better than others. Another way to confirm identification is to examine the extracted values' average variance. A value of 0.5 or higher is recommended.

Table 2 Cross loading result

No.	Indicators	ME 1	ME 2	X1	X2	Y	Z
1	X1 * Z	1.000	0.701	0.118	-0.124	-0.082	-0.262
2	X1.1	0.096	-0.119	0.949	0.366	0.455	0.267
3	X1.2	0.115	-0.118	0.935	0.375	0.433	0.192
4	X1.3	0.130	-0.014	0.582	0.058	0.085	0.037
5	X2 * Z	0.701	1.000	-0.120	-0.214	-0.168	-0.398
6	X2.1	-0.174	-0.178	0.348	0.851	0.853	0.431
7	X2.2	-0.165	-0.207	0.245	0.860	0.643	0.466
8	X2.3	-0.043	-0.192	0.302	0.861	0.719	0.534
9	X2.4	-0.014	-0.134	0.354	0.757	0.626	0.346
10	Y1	-0.032	-0.115	0.425	0.675	0.813	0.480
11	Y2	0.036	-0.087	0.379	0.727	0.855	0.505
12	Y3	-0.095	-0.185	0.381	0.630	0.843	0.522
13	Y4	-0.174	-0.178	0.348	0.851	0.853	0.431
14	Z1	-0.219	-0.279	0.153	0.436	0.470	0.851
15	Z2	-0.228	-0.417	0.214	0.507	0.473	0.883
16	Z3	-0.244	-0.356	0.246	0.471	0.561	0.906

Source: processed field data

Table 3 Average Variance Extracted

No.	Variables	AVE
1	ME 1	1.000
2	ME 2	1.000
3	X1	0.704
4	X2	0.694
5	Y	0.708
6	Z	0.775

Source: processed field data

The table above shows all variables with AVE values greater than 0.5. The X2 variable's minimum AVE value (brand awareness) is 0.694.

4.1.2. Test of reliability

A reliability test is completed by analyzing the reliability values of the configuration from indicator blocks that measure variables. Combined reliability results show best-in-class values of over 0.7. Below is the output of the combined reliability.

The aggregate reliability score for all variables is greater than 0.7, as seen in the above table. As a result, all variables in the anticipated versions meet the criteria for discriminant validity. The lowest combined confidence for the X1 variable (brand image) is 0.873.

Table 4 Composite Reliability

No.	Variables	Composite Reliability
1	ME 1	1.000
2	ME 2	1.000
3	X1	0.873
4	X2	0.901
5	Y	0.906
6	Z	0.912

Source: processed field data

Reliability testing could be check in Cronbach's Alpha values. The output of SmartPLS-3 gives the following results:

Table 5 Cronbach's Alpha

No.	Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
1	ME 1	1.000
2	ME 2	1.000
3	X1	0.808
4	X2	0.853
5	Y	0.863
6	Z	0.855

Source: processed field data

Recommended value is 0.6 or higher. The above desk suggests that Cronbach's alpha values exceed 0.6 for all variables. The lowest value for the X1 variable (brand image) is 0.808.

4.2. Testing the Structural Model (Inner Model)

After model meets the external model criteria. The next step is to check the structural model. The R-squared values of the variables are:

Table 6 R-Square

No.	Variables	R-Square
1	Y	0.787

Source: processed field data

The value of the Y variable 0.787 is shown in the table above. This means that X1, X2, and Z can account for 78.7% of the Y variable.

The test of hypothesis is as below table:

Table 7 Path Coefficients

No.	Variables	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Value
1	X1 → Y	0.153	0.169	0.074	2.071	0.039
2	X2 → Y	0.729	0.719	0.067	10.866	0.000
3	Z → Y	0.178	0.179	0.058	3.099	0.002
4	ME 1 → Y	-0.028	-0.039	0.078	0.355	0.723
5	ME 2 → Y	0.081	0.081	0.070	1.166	0.244

Source: processed field data

From Tables above shows that:

- The relationship between X1 and Y is significant because the P-values are 0.039 (< 0.05). The original sample value is 0.153. indicating that the direction of the connection between X1 and Y is positive. As a result. H1 is accepted.
- The relationship between X2 and Y is significant because the P-values are 0.000 (< 0.05). The original sample value is 0.729. indicating that the direction of the connection between X2 and Y is positive. As a result. H2 is accepted.
- The relationship between Z and Y is significant because P-values are 0.002 (< 0.05). The original sample value is 0.178. indicating that the direction of the connection between Z and Y is positive. As a result. H3 is accepted.
- The relationship between X1 and Y which is moderated by Z is not significant because the P-values are 0.723 (>0.05) and because Z and Y are significant. the brand ambassador (Z) only acts as a predictive moderator in the relationship between brand image (X1) and purchasing decision (Y).
- The relationship between X2 and Y which is moderated by Z is not significant because the P-values are 0.244 (>0.05) and because Z and Y are significant. the brand ambassador (Z) only acts as a predictive moderator in the relationship between brand awareness (X2) and purchasing decision (Y).

In this case. brand image influences purchasing decisions. as evidenced by a feedback questionnaire from respondents who gave a high score to the product statement of the Seiko 5 Sports Watch makes it easy for me to carry out sports activities. and respondents recognize that every product is used must support their activities. However. in order to further improve the brand image. designs that meet the needs of consumers for activities must be maximized.

Brand awareness influences purchasing decisions. as evidenced by the statements of respondents who give a high score to the choice of purchasing the Seiko 5 Sports Watch over other similar watch brands; this demonstrates that efforts to instill memories about the brand yield positive results. Consumers already trust the Seiko brand for all of their watch needs. particularly when it comes to sports activities.

Brand ambassadors influence purchasing decisions. as evidenced by respondents who believe the Seiko 5 Sports Watch product used by professional athletes/Novak Djokovic is of high quality. and respondents who choose the Seiko 5 Sports Watch product because it is used by professional athletes to support their activities. However. even though the brand ambassador has used the Seiko 5 Sports Watch product. this is not the primary reason for his purchase decision.

Brand ambassadors. such as celebrities or other public figures. can assist consumers in making purchasing decisions. This demonstrates that using a celebrity in an advertisement as an endorser raises brand awareness [20]. A brand ambassador has a significant impact on brand awareness [18]. Brand ambassadors significantly and favorably affect a company's reputation. A product's brand image improves with a better brand ambassador. The ideal brand ambassador considers the celebrity's accomplishments and temperament. The compatibility between the brand and the celebrity's personality is the main objective of a brand ambassador. Positive consumer perceptions help to boost the reputation of a product brand. The correct brand ambassador can contribute to enhancing the brand's perception among consumers. Making ensuring that the brand and the endorser's personality mesh together is essential for brand ambassadors. When brand ambassadors include celebrities. the brand's reputation is enhanced. [21]. As a result. celebrities must be chosen in accordance with the product because celebrities will represent the product image [22].

In this study. brand ambassadors cannot moderate the relationship between brand image and brand awareness of purchasing decisions. Therefore. to attract loyal customers to this company. it is necessary to always pay attention to

product quality and re-emphasize increasing brand image and brand awareness. Very complex when a business is on a global scale. to find what customers really want based on Consumer Market Segmentation & International Market Segmentation needs to be done even better to successfully develop a global scale business as well as related to brand ambassadors need to also adjust to Consumer Market Segmentation & International Market Segmentation. If an brand ambassador is well known by the majority of people in certain segments/countries. different results may be possible.

4.3. Managerial Implication

The findings of this study add to knowledge on the connection between brand image. brand awareness. brand ambassadors. and purchase behavior. The results of this study can be used to guide future research and marketing development.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The test results and analysis provide the following conclusions: brand image. brand awareness and brand ambassadors have a direct and significant positive effect on purchasing decisions. Brand ambassadors cannot moderate the relationship between brand image and brand awareness on purchasing decisions.

Therefore. to attract loyal customers to this company. it is necessary to always pay attention to product quality and re-emphasize increasing brand image and brand awareness. Regarding brand ambassadors. it also needs to be adjusted to Consumer Market Segmentation & International Market Segmentation. If a brand ambassador is known by the majority of people in a certain segment/country. different results may occur.

Compliance with ethical standards

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The Author wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

References

- [1] Tjiptono F. Strategi Pemasaran prinsip & penerapan 2020.
- [2] Kamanda SV. Pengaruh Brand Image Dan Price Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Air Minum Merek Sanford (Studi Pada Pelanggan Sinar Mart Jalan R Soeprapto Batam). J AS-SAID 2021;1:19–25.
- [3] Tumanggor R. Hidayat R. Pengaruh Brand Awareness Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian (studi Kasus Indihome Di Kota Bandung Tahun 2018). EProceedings Appl Sci 2018;4.
- [4] Sterie WG. Massie J. Soepono D. Pengaruh Brand Ambassador Dan Brand Image Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Produk Pt. Telesindo Shop Sebagai Distributor Utama Telkomsel Di Manado. J Emba J Ris Ekon Manajemen. Bisnis Dan Akunt 2019;7.
- [5] Gaynor LG. Fashion Marketing Communications E-book 2012.
- [6] Andriani R. Rasto R. Motivasi belajar sebagai determinan hasil belajar siswa. J Pendidik Manaj Perkantoran 2019;4:80–6.
- [7] Sule ET. Saeful K. Pengantar manajemen. Prenada Media; 2019.
- [8] Mayasari H. Kadafi M. Pengaruh Event Sponsorship dan Membership Terhadap Brand Image Family Futsal. Manaj Dan Kewirausahaan 2018;9:36–53.
- [9] Siahaan HD. Yulianti AL. Pengaruh Tingkat Brand Awareness Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Produk Victoria's Secret (studi Pada Konsumen Di Pvj Bandung). EProceedings Manag 2016;3.
- [10] Kotler P. Keller KL. Perilaku Konsumen (sikap dan pemasaran). Terjem Firmansyah. MA Pasuruan CV Penerbit Qiara Media 2018.

- [11] Pradipta D. Hidayat K. Sunarti. Pengaruh Brand Equity Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian (Survei Pada Konsumen Pembeli Dan Pengguna Kartu Perdana Simpati Telkomsel Di Lingkungan Mahasiswa Jurusan Administrasi Bisnis Angkatan 2012 & 2013 Fakultas Ilmu Administrasi Universitas Brawijay. *J Adm Bisnis* n.d.;34.
- [12] Aaker DA. Manajemen Ekuitas Merek. Alih Bahasa: Aris Ananda. Edisi Revisi. Jakarta: Mitra Utama 2010.
- [13] Oktiani A. Khadafi R. Pengaruh Brand Awareness dan Brand Image serta Word Of Mouth terhadap Brand Trust dan Pembentukan Brand Loyalty pada Pelanggan Cbezt Friedchiken Kecamatan Genteng Banyuwangi. *COSTING J Econ Bus Account* 2018;1:269–82.
- [14] Mulyana S. Wirakusumah TK. Hubungan Karakteristik Brand Ambassador Honda Spacy Helm-In dengan Tahapan Keputusan Pembelian Konsumen. *Students E-Journal* 2012;1:27.
- [15] Yusiana R. Maulida R. Pengaruh Gita Gutawa sebagai brand ambassador pond's dalam mempengaruhi keputusan pembelian (studi kasus pada mahasiswi Universitas Telkom jurusan D3 manajemen pemasaran). *J Ecodemica J Ekon Manaj Dan Bisnis* 2015;3:311–6.
- [16] Kennedy JE. Soemanagara RD. Marketing Communication: Taktik dan Strategi. Jakarta PT Buana Ilmu Pop 2006.
- [17] Firmansyah MA. Pemasaran Produk dan Merek: Planning dan Strategy. Penerbit Qiara Media; 2019.
- [18] Sadrabadi AN. Saraji MK. MonshiZadeh M. Evaluating the role of brand ambassadors in social media. *J Mark Manag Consum Behav* 2018;2.
- [19] Alma B. Manajemen pemasaran dan pemasaran jasa 2018.
- [20] Dewi LGPS. Oei SJ. Siagian H. The Effect of Brand Ambassador. Brand Image. and Brand Awareness on Purchase Decision of Pantene Shampoo in Surabaya. Indonesia. 2020.
- [21] Lea-Greenwood G. Fashion marketing communications. John Wiley & Sons; 2013.
- [22] Kotler P. Keller KL. Manajemen pemasaran [Marketing Management]. Jakarta: Erlangga (2012).[in Bahasa Indonesia] n.d.
- [23] Wang F. Hariandja ES. The influence of brand ambassador on brand image and consumer purchasing decision: A case of tous les jours in Indonesia. *Int. Conf. Entrep.* 2016.
- [24] Lee-Greenwood G. Fashion Marketing Communications E-book 2012.
- [25] Sugiyono. Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif. Kualitatif dan R&D. Cetakan Ke-21. Bandung: Alfabeta; 2015.
- [26] Santos A Dos. Analisis Kepuasan Niat Pengguna Terhadap Kualitas Sistem Informasi Akademik Dengan Model Delone Mclean 2017.